

High-Speed Rail as a driver of urban development?

A contrasting comparison of station areas in Germany

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Abstract

The implementation of High-Speed Rail (HSR) is often expected to enhance urban development in municipalities benefitting from improved accessibility. This paper examines HSR as a driver of urban development and provides insights into the underlying interdependencies of urban planning practices and the impacts on urban development achieved or not yet realised. Our study investigates to what extent and in which ways HSR promotes spatial development in small-scale station areas. Thus, we carried out eight contrasting case studies in Germany. By extending previous research, we focussed on spatial impacts in narrowly defined HSR station areas and especially on their municipal planning governance by analysing the respective binding land-use plans (BLUP).

As we will show, impacts are spatially and temporally varied but mainly limited to the immediate station areas, fostering agglomeration effects and new centralities. The case-dependent constraints observed and inherent preconditions witness the need for accompanying municipal planning governance to gain urban development impacts from the HSR-related accessibility improvements.

Furthermore, the analyses presented underpin findings for research and practice, e.g. concerning the lack of integration of rail operations and local urban planning and the importance of consciously embedding HSR in local strategic concepts. Also, we use a new methodical approach to assess the possible impacts of HSR.

Against the backdrop of further HSR expansion in Germany, anticipated but more strategically coordinated urban planning seems promising to exploit the potential for urban development in the station areas.

Keywords

High-Speed Rail, urban development, municipal planning governance, binding land-use plan, transit-oriented development

Introduction

The implementation of High-Speed Rail (HSR) strengthens accessibilities and, thus, HSR stations become key access nodes for long-distance passenger transport. HSR is expected to reduce travel times, replace road and air transport for medium distances and potentially influence the spatial structure in the immediate surroundings of an HSR station – the station area (Banister & Givoni, 2013; Ureña et al., 2009). Various studies have addressed the wide

range of potential impacts of HSR regarding metropolitan integration, real estate markets and land values as well as territorial development in station areas (e.g. Chen et al., 2019; Yin et al., 2015). Still, the critical discussion concerning the HSR's effects on the station area remains ambiguous (Blanquart & Koning, 2017). Nevertheless, positive impacts in the station areas can be assumed due to travel time savings and intermodal connectivity.

In particular, the attractiveness of HSR stations encourages households and firms to (re)locate to their surroundings (Garmendia et al., 2008; Heuermann & Schmieder, 2019). Moreover, high-quality urban development close to railway stations is crucial regarding competition between municipalities to attract firms and residents, the need for sustainable land management due to limited space and desired Transit-Oriented Development (TOD).

However, socioeconomic benefits and spatio-temporal developments, as can be expected in station areas, are outside the scope of classic cost-benefit analyses for transport infrastructures and much more difficult to determine. In this context, wider economic impacts (WEI) are becoming of particular interest in urban and regional studies (Chen & Hall, 2011; Chen & Vickerman, 2017; Holvad & Leleur, 2015). These WEI are attributed to providing self-reinforcing processes or catalytic effects of HSR stations but with no consistent pattern of long-term impacts (Chen et al., 2019). Although agglomeration effects are estimated differently, according to assumptions, these can be spatially extended by HSR (Ahlfeldt & Feddersen, 2018). On the regional level, the largely minimal consensus regards HSR at best as a catalyst rather than a determinant of growth (Yin et al., 2015). Such agglomeration externalities caused by transport infrastructures often unfold their spatial impact only to a limited scale (Graham, 2007). Their analysis is particularly hampered by the lack of disaggregated statistical data below the municipal level.

This study picks up these subjects and deals with HSR station areas in Germany. To exploit the implementation of HSR connection profitably, urban development within station areas presupposes a sufficient absorptive capacity and conscious governance. Thus, the municipalities' governance needs to accompany the HSR potentials prospectively and enable appropriate conditions for spatial development. In Germany, municipalities represent the most fine-grained stage of land-use planning with high autonomy (Danielzyk & Münter, 2018). Against this background, a systematic compilation and assessment of binding land-use plans (BLUP) as the embodiment of municipal planning and underlying strategies seems promising. Therefore, this paper examines how the potential benefits of HSR are mirrored (or not) in the impacts of urban development in station areas and how municipal planning governance addresses these potentials to shape focal points of agglomeration in the station areas.

Theoretical foundations and previous research on urban development in HSR station areas

After the inauguration of HSR in Japan (1964) and its European advent in France (1981), the German era began in 1991 with the ICE (*InterCityExpress*). Now, HSR services operate in more than 15 countries worldwide (UIC, 2021). The different spatial effects have made HSR the subject of analyses by various disciplines. As one aspect, HSR stations form central access points for interregional passenger transport as nodes in the network. Hence, utilising their accessibility effects, new urban developments may emerge around HSR stations (Blanquart & Koning, 2017; Chen et al., 2019).

HSR station areas from node and place perspectives

The envisaged concentration of settlements near railway stations, referred to as TOD, is a far-reaching planning strategy (Ibraeva et al., 2020). Although this planning model is primarily associated with local public transport (PT), it is transferable to HSR stations to value the accessibility advantages of these locations for urban development and pre-empt car-oriented urban sprawl. Furthermore, the general objectives of dense and mixed-use urban areas could be supported by deliberate station-area planning of HSR stations and active land policy (Bertolini et al., 2012; Loukaitou-Sideris & Peters, 2020).

The node-place model (NPM) ascribes railway stations' functions as nodes of frequent and varied PT supplies and places with functional density and mixed-use development around them (Bertolini, 1999). Following this conceptual framework, reconciling both dimensions should be the desired objective of station planning (Loukaitou-Sideris & Peters, 2020). Hence, the challenge involves transferring the emerging node function through an HSR connection into an ambient place.

Some studies point out the positive role of higher-value railway infrastructure than road networks on polycentricity, subcentre formation and higher built-up volumes (Ahlfeldt & Feddersen, 2018; Kasraian et al., 2016). Furthermore, recent research addressed the widespread impact of the size and density of urban areas on economic activities (Graham, 2007; Krehl et al., 2016). As higher densities facilitate the exchange of ideas and knowledge through deriving agglomeration externalities (van Meeteren et al., 2016), HSR station areas may entail locational advantages to the knowledge economy (Blanquart & Koning, 2017; Chen & Hall, 2011; Chen & Vickerman, 2017). In particular, knowledge-intensive activities are named as beneficiaries since they gain profits from (temporary) spatial proximity and face-to-face interactions (Graham, 2007; Growe, 2019; Storper & Venables, 2004; Strambach, 2008), resulting in the possibility of attaining both agglomeration and network externalities (Bentlage et al., 2013; Holvad & Leleur, 2015).

Accordingly, HSR is considered to link both the network scale by higher accessibilities and the agglomeration scale through the capability of higher urban and economic interactions,

especially in station areas (Wenner & Thierstein, 2022). Transferred to the NPM, the node function of HSR stations thus favours network economies through relational proximity between regional, national and international actors, especially due to operational benefits and further expansion. Station areas also become nodes of emerging transport and information exchanges (Bertolini et al., 2012). On the other hand, HSR stations function as places and nuclei of urban development. From this perspective, HSR promotes agglomeration economies through spatial proximity to local and regional actors for knowledge creation.

Previous research on HSR station areas and determining factors for urban development

Regarding previous research, studies on HSR station-area development have mainly been carried out in other European (e.g. in France and Spain) and Asian countries (especially in China and Japan) with varying focuses. These include impacts on real estate markets, company locations, urban quality, and development projects (Beckerich et al., 2019; Chen & Vickerman, 2017; Peters & Novy, 2012; Ribalaygua & Perez-Del-Caño, 2019; Trip, 2008). For HSR in Germany, studies address the economic impacts of increased accessibility via HSR by estimating the strength and spatial scope of agglomeration effects (Ahlfeldt & Feddersen, 2018) and commuting dynamics and decisions concerning the locations of work and residence (Heuermann & Schmieder, 2019). Furthermore, focussing on station areas, Wenner and Thierstein (2022) analyse the generating function of HSR on land-use changes through a Europe-wide investigation, including the German cases, and reveal, inter alia, various urban development impacts depending on regional HSR types. This is completed by the case study by Schütz (1998) regarding the newly built HSR station Kassel-Wilhelmshöhe in which he proves urban densification and a relatively high increase in land and real estate values, especially within the immediate station area (a 5–10 minute walk).

Studies on HSR revealed the high significance of the station location for realised impacts concerning the urban fabric, i.e. whether they are located centrally, on the fringe or on the periphery (Banister & Givoni, 2013; Hall, 2009; Vickerman, 2015). According to Wenner and Thierstein (2022), differences between HSR-station types exist in land-use changes and most developments take place at stations on the urban fringe, as they combine locational attractiveness and available land. Equally, academics emphasise the city's positioning in relation to other cities or the metropolitan embeddedness (Coronado et al., 2019). Regarding their position within HSR corridors, the literature highlights a more complex situation for intermediate stations, since the HSR's potential to redistribute social, economic and spatial conditions has a stronger impact on these locations. Therefore, intermediate cities can gain new metropolitan functions due to HSR (Ureña et al., 2009; Vickerman, 2015).

Current research is twofold in terms of temporal trajectories of developments initiated by HSR. First, studies highlight different dynamics and certain time lags until impacts occur and, second, they differentiate between short-term and long-term effects (Chen et al., 2019; Coronado et al., 2019). In that context, Blanquart and Koning (2017) differentiate short-term

effects, especially on local productivity, consumption and tourism, while the relocation of businesses and households and regional growth appear as long-term effects.

There is ample evidence in the literature of numerous determining factors that lead to the successful development of HSR stations (Bertolini et al., 2012; Mohíno et al., 2014; Ureña et al., 2009). Loukaitou-Sideris and Peters (2020) confirm the notable role of a central station location, among other prerequisites based on a previous survey (Loukaitou-Sideris et al., 2012). Finally, they derive three types of connectivity (operational, intermodal, and spatial) as crucial for HSR station-area planning. Ribalaygua et al. (2020) summarise three developing factors (urban structure, local and regional economic dynamics and specific HSR urban planning strategies). Besides these, available undeveloped or disused land reserves are considered substantial for future developments (Mohíno et al., 2014; Wenner & Thierstein, 2022).

In addition to the abovementioned factors, integration, and cooperation on a multi-level of governance are indispensable preconditions for successful development (Facchinetti-Mannone, 2019; Ribalaygua et al., 2020; Vickerman, 2015). However, in contrast, multi-level governance challenges local strategic planning (Hermelin & Gustafsson, 2022). According to this, municipal planning governance is required and understood as the entirety of municipal planning activities through forms of steering and handling complexities that – in this case – result from the HSR connection. The coordination of formal and informal plans and measures, the strategic coordination of actors and organisations and the handling of the complex local environment are central (Benz & Kilper, 2018). Thus, strategic planning by municipal authorities is an important determinant of efficacious developments in station areas (Mohíno et al., 2014). Some academics consistently argue that the particular context, local circumstances and characteristics would determine the impacts of HSR on urban development to a great extent (Loukaitou-Sideris et al., 2012; Yin et al., 2015). In this context, Wenner and Thierstein (2022) mention the high dependence on discretionary local planning decisions and the high degree of autonomy of sovereign municipal planning. Overall, these remarks underline the interdependence of factors and utilisation of potentials if accompanied by conscious planning and supporting policy measures for HSR to become a station-area development driver.

Planning challenges, research gaps and questions

Nevertheless, divergent positions still exist on the actual development-inducing function of HSR on urban and economic development. According to some critics, HSR would reinforce urban development already underway as a catalyst (Ribalaygua et al., 2020) or primarily serve as a lever rather than a precondition for development projects already planned in the interest of local urban and political motivation (Trip, 2008). On the other hand, studies regard the strong synergies between transport infrastructure and urban dynamics more neutrally, but

state that their high degree of interaction and potential for mutual reinforcement are to be exploited (Yin et al., 2015).

Besides the successful examples of reinvigoration of HSR station areas investigated, the opposite effects of potential drawbacks may also be a consequence of transport infrastructure improvements. On the regional scale, academics discuss the territorial implications of whether HSR leads to regional convergence or divergence (Chen & Vickerman, 2017). Focussing on locally limited impacts, land and real estate prices could rise in the wake of HSR but remain under discussion (Schütz, 1998; Yin et al., 2015), which can lead to gentrification and displacement.

The designation of *successful* planning and development and how to diminish potential drawbacks remains open to interpretation. This discussion is subject to numerous debates in planning theory and exceeds the scope of this article. Thus, in the case of the German planning system, the Federal Building Code (FBC, *Baugesetzbuch*) specifies the mandates of urban land-use planning, including the rather unspecific contribution to "sustainable urban development (...)" (Section 1 (5) FBC). Nevertheless, the literature provides some hints: In the sense of TOD, a mixed-use, polycentric and dense development around PT stations should be achieved as transport and land use become integrated (Ibraeva et al., 2020). More generally, Schütz (1998) states that desirable urban development follows the Model of the European City with the characteristics of density, compactness, centrality, and mixed diversity of uses.

Most investigations on the urban development impacts of HSR are mainly carried out as descriptive case study comparisons in different contexts (Mohíno et al., 2014; Peters & Novy, 2012; Ribalaygua et al., 2020; Ribalaygua & Perez-Del-Caño, 2019). Moreover, except for the recent quantitative study on European countries by Wenner and Thierstein (2022), no study has so far compared German HSR station areas in detail. This underlines a lack of evidence as to which preconditions and factors are crucial for successful alterations in the station area, especially the extent to which interwoven processes operate. Furthermore, the meta-analysis of Cheng and Chen (2022) on the socioeconomic impacts of HSR underpins the general need for further research on HSR in Germany, since they include the only two existing regional economic studies so far (Ahlfeldt & Feddersen, 2018; Heuermann & Schmieder, 2019).

Based on this background, these remarks pose new questions on the achieved and as yet unrealised impacts of HSR on urban development and their underlying drivers and interdependencies, especially in the German context. Furthermore, deeper insight into the municipalities' strategies and the anticipation of governance for the given HSR potential is helpful to grasp the basic processes and understand how HSR is being integrated into planning and policy (Bertolini et al., 2012; Hermelin & Gustafsson, 2022).

To contribute to this research, we investigated the spatio-temporal urban development due to HSR and depicted the respective municipalities' strategies in the German context. Furthermore, we also intended a conceptual advancement determining the HSR station areas'

potential and requirements for becoming a place for urban development (Bertolini, 1999). To address this topic, we considered two research questions:

Q1: What impacts does the introduction of HSR have on station-area development and in which spatial and temporal manifestations do they appear?

Q2: How does municipal planning governance address this potential and what are other inherent preconditions for urban development?

Methodical approach and case studies

Research subject: High-Speed Rail in Germany

HSR commonly covers newly built lines equipped for at least 250kph or upgraded lines for speeds of 200kph (European Council, 1996). However, this study focuses on HSR services with speeds of 250kph or more, since accessibility improvements are expected to be significantly higher compared to those for roads. Accordingly, today's German HSR network comprises 31 stations exclusively serving passenger transport and the vast majority have the train category *InterCityExpress* (ICE).

The polycentric spatial structure of Germany is also reflected in the railway structure: Compared to other European countries with a more radially-oriented network towards a single metropolis, the HSR network is more fragmented between several metropolitan/regional centres, with some regions not directly connected. In addition, the history of the division of Germany ensured that capacity bottlenecks were eliminated, especially stepwise on North-South routes (Figure 1). Moreover, due to the HSR network having mostly evolved historically on upgraded conventional lines, supplemented by just a few new lines, most stations are in inner-city locations. Unlike at stations in undeveloped areas on the urban fringe or in the periphery, which is more prevalent on an international comparison, this situation leads to challenges in terms of urban developments in already built-up areas, where the introduction of HSR may further increase pressure on land use. Simultaneously, this situation leads to a good integration of HSR with the city centres and to local PT, but conversely also to a higher station density and thus not to maximised travel time gains (Ahlfeldt & Feddersen, 2018; Wenner & Thierstein, 2022). The multi-level system of comprehensive spatial planning in Germany is based on the task of coordinating different, partly competing, demands on (land-)use. This integrated character is interrelated to sectoral planning, such as transport planning (including HSR). This privileged infrastructural planning serves to weigh up and balance sectoral tasks and measures by using spatially relevant procedures for planning approval (Danielzyk & Münter, 2018; Schmidt-Eichstaedt, 2018). Since the implementation of federal railways is directly entrusted to a federal higher authority and based on an upstream requirements plan (*Bundesverkehrswegeplan*; Federal Ministry of Transport and Digital Infrastructure (2016)), the negotiating power of municipalities – as the lowest level of spatial

planning and different to local land-use planning – to influence route alignment and station locations is very limited (Pahl-Weber & Henckel, 2008). Furthermore, the railway company *Deutsche Bahn* owns and administers most of the railway infrastructure and long-distance trains.

This predetermining character of infrastructure provision results in research interest in how municipalities anticipate and mesh with the new infrastructural impetus of HSR with local land-use planning in station areas.

Contrasting case studies

According to the explanations in the chapter above, the case of the German HSR network presents particularities which challenge a detailed investigation. To comply with this circumstance, we chose eight HSR stations in Germany with their station areas as case studies (Table 1) for our comparative analysis following the strategy of maximum variation cases (Flyvbjerg, 2006).

Unlike as is often the case with centrally located main stations in core cities, stations located outside urban regions benefit more from the travel time gains of the substantial HSR expansion. So, half of our cases are located outside urban regions (Figure 1) to better isolate the potential impacts of a higher relative increase in accessibility. Erfurt's station, as chosen case of a main station in a core city, is a notable exception, as new HSR lines have recently resulted in significant gains in accessibility. In particular, the case studies of the medium-sized cities of Fulda, Montabaur and Bamberg are located outside urban regions. In contrast, Ingolstadt, although also outside, is a large-sized city in terms of its inhabitants. In contrast, the cases of Siegburg/Bonn and Vaihingen(Enz) form stations in the vicinity of core cities (Cologne/Bonn and Stuttgart respectively), resulting in potentially different preconditions for station area development. Finally, the case of Cologne Messe/Deutz is significant, since the secondary station within a core city marks the end of a newly-built HSR line.

In addition to the common characteristic of improved accessibility, the cases represent a wide range in the year of HSR implementation. Both short and long periods can be observed – starting with the inauguration of HSR in 1991 to the most recent HSR openings in Germany in 2017. Other distinguishing traits are the number of inhabitants – but at the same time representing the characteristic of the German HSR network of more frequent stops in medium-sized cities – as well as the location within the urban fabric (see maps in the Appendix for details) and whether a station has been upgraded or – rarer in Germany – newly built.

Figure 1: HSR network in Germany and case studies

Geodata: GeoBasis-DE/BKG 2020; Data: Fina et al., 2020; Deutsche Bahn 2021

	Year of HSR implementation	Inhabitants (municipality, 2019)	Services on weekdays (long-distance passenger rail)		Status	Station location (to city centre)	Regional location	Connection to PT ²	Parking spaces (radius of 500m)
			before HSR	in 2019					
Fulda	1991	69,000	94	136	upgraded	central	station in medium-sized city outside urban region ¹	mid	1,530
Vaihingen(Enz)³	1991	45,000	-	38	newly built	edge	station in vicinity of core city	low	980
Köln (Cologne) Messe/Deutz	2002	1,088,000	2	54	upgraded	central/edge	secondary station in core city	high	2,210
Montabaur	2002	40,000	-	36	newly built	edge	station in medium-sized city outside urban region	low	1,400
Siegburg/Bonn	2002	42,000	20	73	upgraded	central	station in vicinity of core city	high	2,200
Ingolstadt Hbf	2006	137,000	27	67	upgraded	central/edge	station in large-sized city outside urban region	mid	1,330
Erfurt Hbf	2015	214,000	47	110	upgraded	central	main station in core city	high	470
Bamberg	2017	77,000	36	32	upgraded	central	station in medium-sized city outside urban region	mid	380

Table 1: Characteristics of the case studies

Sources: BBSR Bonn, 2022; Grahnert & Krings, 2021; parking spaces: retrieved from parkenambahnhof.de, parkopedia.de and municipality websites

¹ Fina et al., 2020

² refers to connection by local bus, tram-/subway and local/regional trains

³ currently mainly served by InterCity/EuroCity trains

Delimiting the station area

Depending on the examination objective, station areas have different and context-specific delimitations (Guerra et al., 2012; Yin et al., 2015). However, no universal definition exists, but common thresholds as buffers range between 500m and 800m ('half-mile circle') and sometimes up to 1km (García-Palomares et al., 2013; Guerra et al., 2012; Otsuka et al., 2019). The consensus, however, is that some HSR effects are limited to a short range and that certain agglomeration effects rapidly diminish (van Meeteren et al., 2016).

Since analyses at this level are elusive via aggregated data available only at the level of administrative units, we attempted to capture the possible impacts empirically precisely through small-scale delimitations of the catchment areas. Therefore, we decided to combine different delimitations considering the individual conditions – in terms of walkability (Otsuka et al., 2019) and spatial connectivity (Loukaitou-Sideris & Peters, 2020) – and to provide a case-independent spatial classification across all cases. In contrast to previous studies, we attempted to construct the analysis holistically by defining three different thresholds to address possible distance-related differences.

Firstly, following the 'walkable radius' of 700m from the main pedestrian entrance set by Bertolini (1999), we set a walkable isochrone of 800m that appropriately transfers the radius to the built-up area¹. Furthermore, 300m walkable isochrones were used to examine the "primary development zone" (Yin et al., 2015) even more closely. This corresponds to a five-minute walk. These two small-scale thresholds of walkable isochrones of 300m and 800m start at the station entrances and are based on the pedestrian infrastructure with *OpenRouteService* to define the immediate station area (ISA).

To capture possible impacts beyond the ISA as well, we implemented a further delimitation with a grid of 3x3km – excluding the ISA – referred to as the wider station area (WSA). This approach is based on the synergies observed between the HSR and the surrounding locations but without denoting exact metric values for delimitation (Yin et al., 2015) so that we made the explorative determination to empirically examine whether impacts of HSR radiate further beyond the often-described narrow catchment areas.

The individual surface areas of the delimited ISA differ from the average of 27.1ha (for a 300m isochrone) and 154.9ha (for an 800m isochrone) (see Table 2). The shapes of the ISA for 800m in Vaihingen(Enz) and Montabaur reflect the new construction in advance of the HSR implementation well. In both cases, we find agricultural uses in at least one cardinal direction according to which urban structures concentrate in the axes of entrances. The other cases provide a much higher spatial embeddedness into their surroundings (see maps in the Appendix).

¹ share of 800m isochrones covering 700m radius: max = 0.993, min = 0.669, mean = 0.886

The nature of binding land-use plans (BLUP) and the method of document analysis

The Federal Building Code (FBC) is the most important legal framework of urban development in Germany, according to which local authorities regulate "urban development and the structure of their territories by means of urban land-use planning in their own responsibility" (Pahl-Weber & Henckel, 2008; Section 2 (1) FBC). To fulfil this task, local authorities can rely on the preparatory land-use plan (*Flächennutzungsplan*) outlining the types of land use envisaged for the entire municipal territory and on the binding land-use plan (*Bebauungsplan*, BLUP), defining more concrete and legally binding stipulations to steer urban developments and land use for buildings or other purposes (Pahl-Weber & Henckel, 2008; Schmidt-Eichstaedt, 2018; Section 8 (1) FBC). Therefore, BLUP represent sovereign municipal planning decisions (Sections 1–3 FBC).

We compiled legally binding BLUP starting ten years before the announcement of the HSR track alignment and stations to address the research questions. The BLUP cover intended activities in a comparable way across all case studies. Accordingly, smaller building projects carried out without a BLUP procedure are occasionally not included in the analyses.

Generally consisting of a plan and an explanatory memorandum (Pahl-Weber & Henckel, 2008), we subjected parts of the BLUP to structured content analysis (White & Marsh, 2006) and transferred the information into a tabular overview and into GIS. The BLUP of adjacent municipalities captured by the 3x3km WSA were also included. In the explanatory memorandum of the BLUP (Section 9 (8) FBC), we searched for keywords related to HSR. Additionally, we provided an excerpt of the intended land use or stipulations and whether the plans establish preconditions for knowledge-intensive activities. We also considered the connotation of HSR in the form of positive associations or potential drawbacks.

The classification of the BLUP took place as follows (Figure 2): BLUP with reference to HSR were examined as to whether the respective area was already developed at the time of legal binding or not by checking satellite images of the respective dates. If not, the type of land-use transformation is (a) development of hitherto open spaces. If the area was already developed, we checked for the intended type of building use. If the planned use differed from the previous urban structure, e.g. from commercial to residential use, the type of land-use transformation is (b) conversion of existing structures. Otherwise, if no different type of building use was intended, the type of land-use transformation is (c) retention of existing uses. Subsequently, we compared the status of realisation ($\geq 50\%$ of the BLUP plot developed with the intended and permitted uses) using current satellite images. Finally, we checked for the status of implementation (legally binding BLUP or still in preparation). All data was collected to November 2021.

Figure 2: Method for classification of the BLUP (Source: own conception)

To consolidate the municipal planning characteristics (Table 3), we mainly reviewed the explanatory memorandum of the BLUP and complemented this with further planning and policy documents and information from the local authorities.

Results on urban development impacts and municipal planning governance in the context of HSR

Urban development in the station areas

The results comprise evaluations of 396 BLUP, ranging from 16 (Montabaur) to 104 (Siegburg). Of these, 65 BLUP (16%) directly refer to HSR in their explanatory memoranda. At the time of analysis, 58 BLUP (15%) were in preparation of which 19 were related to HSR. Therefore, further analyses concentrated on the HSR-referenced BLUP, both legally binding (46) or currently in preparation (19). The earliest plan dealing with HSR came up 13 years before HSR's introduction (Siegburg). However, this stands out compared to other cases where the first plan became legally binding closer to the opening year or much later (Table 2). Differences also exist regarding the number of BLUP, but these cannot inevitably be linked to the years of HSR operation. Ingolstadt is notable, since its first HSR-referenced BLUP is currently in preparation.

The analysis of spatial impacts (as BLUP surface areas) revealed a highly differentiated reflection within the ISA. Figure 3 contains all parts of BLUP that permit the construction of buildings, differentiated by the type of land-use transformation and status of realisation.

An initial view revealed that a high share of the legally binding projects has already been realised. Despite the significantly smaller surface area, the overall spatial impacts of realised developments in the 300m isochrones (approx. 44.0ha) were almost identical to those in the 800m isochrones (approx. 46.4ha).

	Fulda	Vaihingen (Enz)	Köln (Cologne) Messe/Deutz	Montabaur	Siegburg/ Bonn	Ingolstadt Hbf	Erfurt Hbf	Bamberg
Year of opening	1991	1991	2002	2002	2002	2006	2015	2017
First BLUP with reference to HSR (Δ to)	2003 (+12)	1993 (+2)	2003 (+1)	2000 (-2)	1989 (-13)	2022 (+16) ¹	2010 (-5)	2019 (+2)
Qty. of BLUP with reference to HSR (of which in preparation)	4 (0)	7 (1)	11 (3)	10 (1)	18 (3)	1 (1)	7 (5)	7 (5)
Surface area of ISA (ha)²	300m 23.2	23.6	37.7	20.2	25.2	31.8	30.2	24.9
	800m 155.4	144.4	166.6	107.6	154.0	172.3	178.9	160.0

Table 2: Descriptive results of the case studies

Source: own calculation based on the BLUP of the case studies

¹ Approximate, since the BLUP draft was approved by the local council (28/10/2021) in a preparatory stage before becoming legally binding. Therefore, it is expected to be legally binding in 2022.

² See maps in the Appendix

Figure 3: Spatial impacts of HSR within the ISA (in ha)

Type of land-use transformation: a = development of hitherto open spaces; b = conversion of existing structures; c = retention of existing uses (Source: own calculation based on the BLUP of the case studies)

However, when dividing by type of transformation, high case dependence is shown. The development of hitherto open spaces (a) occurs in both zones of the ISA; and the newly built stations (Montabaur, Vaihingen(Enz)) are remarkable. Furthermore, the likewise older stations indicate re-densification on hitherto open spaces (Fulda, C-Messe/Deutz² and Siegburg). All of these are mainly mixed and commercial areas. Conversions of existing structures (b) provide much more differentiated patterns. For the most part, developments are largely completed for the older cases but not yet for newer stations, suggesting that transitions are taking longer compared to initial developments. Retention of existing uses (c) occurs with two intentions. Firstly, these are realised replacements or new buildings of the same type. Secondly, these represent targeted governance for further development and maintenance of current structures mitigating undesirable urban developments. Some of the BLUP intend to maintain the established inner-city functions in the spatial connection between the station and the city centre and advance the structures anticipating HSR implementation (Fulda, Montabaur, Siegburg and Erfurt). Type (c) also involves new

² C-Messe/Deutz = Köln (Cologne) Messe/Deutz

buildings retaining existing uses initiated by the high accessibility increase. Predominantly, developments in the ISA are heterogeneous mixed and commercial use.

The cases confirm a threshold of pedestrian catchment area beyond which development impulses decline. Therefore, we also disclosed the spatial impacts within the WSA – excluding the ISA – to control for the assumption of decreasing agglomeration effects (van Meeteren et al., 2016) (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Spatial impacts of HSR within the WSA (in ha)

Type of land-use transformation: a = development of hitherto open spaces; b = conversion of existing structures; c = retention of existing uses (Source: own calculation based on the BLUP of the case studies)

Unlike in the ISA, urban developments in the WSA can only be detected in six cases. Apart from the outstanding development (commercial area primarily for forwarding and logistic provider) in Vaihingen(Enz) on former agricultural land (a), significant brownfield developments as (b) the conversion of existing structures only take place to a greater extent in the WSA of highly integrated HSR stations that can extend or even generate spill-over effects to the wider surroundings (commercial area in C-Messe/Deutz, realised, and mixed and residential areas in Erfurt, envisaged). In such cases, the rezoning of former railway areas becomes a lever, but less so than in the ISA. In the other cases with predominantly integrated station locations, developments appear less pronounced. This can be attributed to already having dense surroundings or areas with restrictions nearby.

Furthermore, with increasing distance to the station, a change in the projected uses is discernible towards a higher degree of residential use. The outer area developments in several cases include various types of newly erected residential buildings (C-Messe/Deutz, Montabaur, Siegburg and Erfurt). On the other hand, in the case of (a) developments on hitherto open spaces, planning occasionally needs to be adjusted due to nature conservation. For example, a site of residential area planning in Montabaur was reduced due to biotope protection (size reduced from 2.9ha to 1.3ha).

Although the total size of the BLUP with reference to HSR is larger in the WSA (80.6ha realised, 25.1ha not yet realised), this significance is reduced when the respective share of the total area of the zones is considered. Apparently, the external area effects triggered by HSR are only of subordinate importance and solely occur under corresponding preconditions.

Overall spatial impacts and temporal trajectories

The calculated overall spatial impact (as surface areas of all the BLUP related to HSR in the ISA and WSA) is approx. 259.0ha, of which about 179.4ha include realised and about 79.6ha not yet realised developments. As discussed before, based on the spatial subdivision in ISA and WSA, these values differ significantly between the cases and depending on the type of building use (Figure 5). Focussing on the aggregated shares of each type, commercial areas are in the majority (35%), followed by mixed areas (26%). Residential areas account for 21% of spatial impacts, special areas are of lesser relevance (10%) and public facilities, traffic areas and green spaces add up to about 7%.

Figure 5: Overall spatial impacts of HSR: Area size by types of building use, within the ISA and WSA (in ha)

Other = public facilities + traffic areas + green spaces (Source: own calculation based on the BLUP of the case studies)

It is worth reporting that there is a certain surplus within the unimplemented uses, since 37% of the areas earmarked in the BLUP for commercial and 35% for mixed use are not yet realised. In contrast, 86% of the intended residential areas are realised. Besides the previously analysed built-up areas, the BLUP define stipulations of green spaces and traffic areas as land-use categories. Both the newly built and the upgraded existing HSR stations require transport access. Thus, appropriate access via road is a precondition for urban developments and PT integration as well. Due to the already often accessible station areas, new traffic areas are insignificant in the present cases overall. Only some BLUP contain stipulations for the initial provision of new development areas by transport infrastructure (especially Siegburg and C-Messe/Deutz).

Regarding the temporal trajectories of municipal planning, the disaggregated quantity of BLUP in Figure 6 highlights the highest number of legally binding BLUP related to HSR in the first phase (+1 – +5 years) after HSR implementation, especially with the peak of 13 BLUP referring to HSR within the ISA. However, the first pre-initial phase (-5 – -1 years) is equally interesting, with a similarly high number of eight legally binding BLUP.

Figure 6: Year the BLUP became legally binding in relation to the respective year of HSR implementation, within the ISA and WSA, cumulated for all case studies

Source: own calculation based on the BLUP of the case studies

However, in the same phases, the nascent BLUP unrelated to HSR (but located primarily in the WSA) are numerous, indicating a strong planning impetus or emerging developments around the time of HSR implementation. In total, the most BLUP related to HSR arose in the first 15 years (31 of 46). Certain temporal outliers are also worth mentioning, with one plan already 13 years before (station forecourt, Siegburg) and several plans more than 25 years after HSR implementation (e.g. district development, Fulda).

From this analysis, we can, on the one hand, deduce a spatially concentrated development potential of HSR predominantly in the ISA, indicating small-scale spill-over effects. On the other hand, the planning activities related to HSR concentrate on the phase 5 years before and the first 15 years after implementation. This suggests anticipation of the HSR potentials with short- to medium-term impulses. Nevertheless, Figure 6 only includes the 46 currently legally binding BLUP related to HSR. 19 more BLUP are currently in preparation and distributed across seven cases (Table 2). This pattern reveals different and continuous municipal planning processes and long-term impacts. However, a concentration on the two newest HSR stations (Erfurt and Bamberg) is recognisable, each with five BLUP in preparation.

In-depth case study comparison concerning municipal planning governance

Based on the determining factors for urban development in HSR station areas previously extracted from the literature (e.g. Loukaitou-Sideris et al., 2012; Mohíno et al., 2014; Ribalaygua et al., 2020; Yin et al., 2015) and the emphasis of municipal planning and governance (Hermelin & Gustafsson, 2022; Wenner & Thierstein, 2022), we derived items that either describe crucial facets of local governance or are further inherent preconditions closely related to local governance (Benz & Kilper, 2018). By partially adjusting the items to the present case study conditions, we obtained seven main groups to gain detailed insights into the municipal planning governance with reference to the research questions. Table 3 serves as a case study comparison. Therefore, the respective documents of each case are aggregated in terms of content to superordinated statements.

	Fulda	Vaihingen (Enz)	Köln (Cologne) Messe/Deutz	Montabaur	Siegburg/ Bonn	Ingolstadt Hbf	Erfurt Hbf	Bamberg
Framing and marketing	-	Perfekter Standort (' <i>Perfect Location</i> ', marketing title for commercial area)	renaming the station to Köln Messe/Deutz (2004) MesseCity Köln (building complex) ICE-Terminal (name of the BLUP)	ICE-Park (development area with character as a city district) Aubachviertel (commercial and mixed-use district)	renaming the station to Siegburg/Bonn (2002)	-	ICE-City Erfurt (umbrella brand)	-
Planning strategies	positioning as a venue and strengthening tourism inner-urban residential development (rental housing) urban-spatial connection to the city centre retention but also upgrading of station district	commercial and residential areas serve as supplement to the heavily congested core area of the Stuttgart Region separation of functions	expansion of trade fair, congress and hotel industry large-scale development of mixed service districts punctual densification in the ISA	development of business centre (nearby) and residential areas urban-spatial connection to the city centre retention of residential building character in adjacent district separation of functions	prospective development of a mixed-use district in the ISA densification of residential uses in the WSA urban-spatial connection to the city centre sites for higher-value services on stations' rear side (not yet realised)	alleviating development deficiencies (recently announced)	development of high-quality district on former railway area urban-spatial connection to the city centre retention but also upgrading of station district with higher-value services	green spaces and axis along the tracks as compensation for HSR enlargement
Formal instruments and informal concepts <i>formal instruments (in italics)</i>	urban development concept (in preparation) urban design competitions (2019 and 2017)	-	architecture competitions (2x 2016 and 2000) framework development concept (2009) urban design competition (2002)	urban design competition (2019) framework development plan (1994, modified) <i>Urban Development Measure (1994–2017)</i>	urban master plan (2019) urban design competition (1995)	concept of structural considerations (2018) concept regulating high-rise buildings (2016)	planning competitions (2020 and 2019) integrated urban concept (2015) framework development plan (2013) <i>formally designated rehabilitation areas (since 2001 and 1996)</i>	landscape architectural conception (2021) <i>formally designated rehabilitation area (since 2008)</i>

	Fulda	Vaihingen (Enz)	Köln (Cologne) Messe/Deutz	Montabaur	Siegburg/ Bonn	Ingolstadt Hbf	Erfurt Hbf	Bamberg
Local constraints and characteristics	rear side characterised by railway use	surrounded by agricultural land in use	station area characterised by trade fair, multi-purpose hall and Rhine promenade UNESCO-heritage Cologne cathedral: permission of high-rise buildings denied (2001–06)	A3 motorway directly north surrounded by agricultural land in use	retention area (Sieg river) limits developments	HSR station apart from the city centre, surrounded by residential areas rear side characterised by industrial and commercial use big (cargo) tracks in use	some brownfields that will take time for transition	UNESCO-heritage area adjacent to the station
Relevant construction works directly at the station	redesign of station square and adjacent pedestrian zone	new building construction along new tracks and closure of the former station	redesign of the station square newly built connection and entrance to trade fair	new building construction along new tracks and closure of the former station	new building construction and integration of tramway in the basement redesign of the station square	redesign of the station square new construction of the entrance building (planned)	comprehensive reconstruction	redesign of station square (planned)
Larger urban development projects	mixed district (4.3ha), planned	residential area (21.8ha) commercial area (41ha)	mixed districts (12.7ha and 5.4ha / 130,000sqm GFA) ¹	business district (35,000sqm GFA) mixed-use district (5.1ha) FOC ² (10,000sqm shop floor)	mixed district (8.5ha), planned	high-rise building as new station building (18,000sqm GFA), planned area of former postal site (1.0ha), planned	two high-rise buildings (26,000sqm GFA), planned business districts (22.8ha and 2.9ha), planned	sustainable mixed district (1.5ha), being realised
Land conversion and further prospective areas	prospective conversion of allotment garden area	preparatory land-use plan: large extensions on agricultural land (42ha)	demolition of a residential area regeneration of large industrial brownfields	regeneration of former railway area prospective extension of FOC and of commercial areas	prospective redevelopment of inner-city district	prospective redevelopment of the former postal site	prospective regeneration of former freight station site, railway depot and former brewery site	-

Table 3: Consolidation of specific municipal planning characteristics in the case study comparison

Source: own compilation based on the BLUP and further planning documents of the case studies

¹ GFA = gross floor area; ² FOC = Factory-Outlet Centre

Framing and marketing

Since HSR station-area projects are often designed as comprehensive infrastructure measures with the potential for greater urban development, a framing or marketing of such developments could enlarge the possible impacts. Therefore, a supportive framing of projects could enhance HSR's allure and union actors under an umbrella brand or a marketing slogan respectively. Some of the chosen cases (C-Messe/Deutz, Montabaur and Erfurt) reflect these considerations, as they use the brand ICE as a well-known type of train for framing and bundling their planning activities.

Planning strategies

In all cases, the planning strategies pursued are either explicitly expressed within the BLUP or additional plans or can be inferred implicitly. The temporal dimension and spatial scope are very specific. They range from early initiated large-scale district developments (Vaihingen(Enz), Montabaur, C-Messe/Deutz and Erfurt) to considerably later structural changes in the surrounding areas (Ingolstadt) and punctual interventions respectively (C-Messe/Deutz and Siegburg). The large-scale concentration of jobs in (higher-value) service and non-manufacturing sectors (Montabaur, Erfurt, C-Messe/Deutz and Siegburg) is probably the largest development path for directly adjacent areas.

In line with that, new urban mixed-use districts near the station represent another pillar and have already been realised (C-Messe/Deutz and Montabaur) or are in planning / gradual realisation (Erfurt and Siegburg). In contrast, more mono-functional residential districts also appear, especially to cope with increased accessibility due to HSR and spill-over effects from the better linked metropolitan areas (Vaihingen(Enz) to Stuttgart and Fulda to Frankfurt am Main). Furthermore, a new metropolitan integration of more distant cities via HSR widening the labour and residential market is also evident in Montabaur and Siegburg (both with new connections to the Frankfurt am Main metropolitan area; for Montabaur, also to Cologne and Bonn), which triggered residential development (Garmendia et al., 2008; Mohíno et al., 2014).

The urban-spatial connection of the HSR station to nearby city centres means that a different planning strategy is being pursued by seizing on existing urban qualities and enhancing connection axes and public spaces (e.g. pedestrian zones) (Trip, 2008).

Retaining existing structures is a striking planning strategy, more visible in the established station areas and highly dependent on individual conditions. The common underlying motives are mitigating negative developments and potential drawbacks in the context of HSR. These include the displacement of established retail and specific population segments (Schütz, 1998) with simultaneous positive planning specifications for future developments (Fulda, Montabaur and Erfurt). Regulations made significantly later after HSR implementation (Fulda: +12 years and Montabaur: +19 years) highlight the long-lasting

processes of urban development due to HSR and the need for permanent governance and adaptation of strategies.

Formal instruments and informal concepts

As part of HSR station-area development, some cases employ further formal instruments of German planning law besides BLUP. For example, the instrument of Urban Rehabilitation Measures is also frequently used in different contexts to alleviate urban deficits in a specific area (Pahl-Weber & Henckel, 2008; Section 136–164 FBC). However, traditional station areas often require redevelopment and fulfil the necessary preconditions (Erfurt and Bamberg). Further, the instrument of Urban Development Measures is available to develop specific areas according to their desired development for the first time or to redevelop such areas within the framework of urban renewal with public interest (Pahl-Weber & Henckel, 2008; Section 165–171 FBC). Therefore, it is the only instrument permitting the municipality full and independent development from the planning to the marketing of a new district, as in the case of Montabaur. In addition, both instruments enable the partial refinancing of the desired urban development through planning-related increases in value (the difference in the market value prior to and after the measure) when the land ready for building is repurchased.

Additional informal concepts often accompany urban planning or other formal instruments. Due to their flexibility, problem-focus on local conditions and varying degree of detail (Pahl-Weber & Henckel, 2008), we see their frequent use and great range across the case studies. Trends concerning the station type and embeddedness into urban fabric can be seen. Most of these concepts were arranged in C-Messe/Deutz and Erfurt, which exhibits the complexity of planning demands in high-density, mixed-use areas in transition.

The year of finalisation is noteworthy, since most plans only emerged several years after HSR implementation, illustrating the continuing process and possible later occurrence of urban development impacts. Just six of the total 19 informal concepts considered were established in advance or in the year of HSR implementation. Nevertheless, the early beginning of the formal instruments is worth noting, as it confirms their mandatory and long-term character.

Local constraints and characteristics

Despite some cross-case patterns, the highly case-specific peculiarities are evident, leading to different forms of pressure on local development. However, urban structures which have evolved due to a rail connection created more than a century ago are common. On the one hand, this persistence of built-up areas hampers rapid developments. In addition to the resulting embeddedness into the urban fabric, case-specific constraints emerge, such as larger (but often in use) railway areas (Fulda, Ingolstadt and Erfurt), distinctive uses (C-Messe/Deutz and Ingolstadt) or areas for non-settlement or traffic (Vaihingen(Enz),

Montabaur and Siegburg). On the other hand, some cases show significant softer factors bindingly influencing planning opportunities, like UNESCO world heritage sites (C-Messe/Deutz and Bamberg) or regulations on high-rise buildings (Ingolstadt).

Relevant construction work directly at the station

As the linchpin providing node and (resulting) place functions (Bertolini, 1999), the station itself takes centre stage for possible impacts. In addition to the inherent completely new construction in the case of new HSR stations, enhancements are often required for existing stations to provide HSR services.

In all cases, HSR became better integrated into the local PT system by placing the central bus station nearby (node function) if it was not already there (Fulda, Vaihingen(Enz), Montabaur and Siegburg). Ingolstadt and C-Messe/Deutz, where the HSR stations represent just the second most important station for PT within the city, are exceptions. In addition, HSR implementation accompanies the construction of numerous parking spaces in many cases.

Furthermore, urban planning measures, like redesigning station squares and adjacent public spaces, foster the place function. Place-building elements also include better linking to the city centre (see "planning strategies") and of the previous station rear sides to access HSR (C-Messe/Deutz, Siegburg and Ingolstadt).

Larger urban development projects

The cases shown confirm the often raised expectations for urban development impacts from HSR to various extents. However, the diverse impacts impede analytical conclusions since the types of use tend to differ from some mono-functional districts to those with mixed use. In addition, the individual sizes range from 1ha up to 40ha. Nevertheless, project-based urban development is apparent (Peters & Novy, 2012; Trip, 2008). Often bigger private developers or investors accelerate the realisation process for which the FBC also provides the special form of project-based BLUP (Section 11–12 FBC). In addition, some outstanding projects or solitary buildings, all of which have an extraordinary impact on address generation, accompany ordinary urban development. These flagship projects include, for example, hotel or congress centres, high-rise buildings, multi-purpose building complexes or the unique Factory-Outlet Centre in Montabaur.

Land conversion and further prospective areas

According to the quantitative results, the significance of land provision is immense for spatial developments induced by HSR (Mohíno et al., 2014; Wenner & Thierstein, 2022). Conversions seem to provide a high potential, especially in existing station areas. Some cases reflect the big lever of redeveloping abandoned sites. Particularly noteworthy, however, are displacements of existing uses in favour of higher-value developments (Fulda and

C-Messe/Deutz). On the other hand, newly built HSR stations show the logical utilisation of suitable land for extensions on the urban fringe, fostering integration into the urban fabric. As a result, a new centrality with significant new businesses emerged in Montabaur. However, in Vaihingen(Enz), no agglomeration is observable in the ISA. Some cases illustrate ongoing processes and the frequent interim use of zoned sites as parking spaces until buildings are erected (Siegburg, Montabaur and Erfurt).

Discussion: High-Speed Rail as a driver of urban development?

Impacts of HSR on station-area development and manifestations (Q1)

Our analyses encompass 65 BLUP with direct references to HSR and provide the following issues for discussion. The BLUP have a total surface area of 259ha, of which developments in the size of 179ha (70%) are realised. Commercial (35% of the surface area) and mixed use (26%) are the majority of intended use. Residential use accounts for 21%, followed by special areas with about 10%. The varying degree of realisation is noteworthy, ranging from 82% (residential) to 63% (commercial).

First, assigning these findings into case characteristics (Table 1) shows tendencies depending on the city's size and the type of station. However, correlations between the number of HSR services and the spatial impacts are difficult to state. An increase in higher accessibility alone does not automatically lead to distinctive urban developments.

Second, the spatial distinction in the ISA and WSA highlights significant agglomeration effects in the vicinity of HSR stations but rapidly declining effects outwards. We can reveal pronounced impacts concentrated in the ISA with mainly mixed and commercial use. A tendency toward a higher density is recognisable, since the defined types of building use allow for a greater floor area ratio (Krehl et al., 2016). Therefore, new centralities emerge with a concentration of new businesses around some stations (Volgmann & Münter, 2018). However, distance-specific phenomena occur, since the 800m isochrones already include big areas not yet realised and the significance of residential areas rises simultaneously. The rather singular impacts in the WSA point to the presumed further preconditions.

Third, when distinguishing the type of land-use transformation, the sample reveals highly case-dependent patterns which prevent generalisations. However, some parallels are obvious. Type (a), development of hitherto open spaces, is more present in newly built station areas and as re-densification in older ones. The typical development path of type (b), conversion of existing structures, suggests that conversions take longer and need greater effort than initial developments. The emergence of type (c), retention of existing uses, is twofold: These are replacements of buildings with the same type or – especially in established station areas – the targeted governance for further development but maintaining of current urban structures.

In terms of temporal trajectories, the most BLUP related to HSR emerged 5 years before and 15 years after HSR implementation. However, the date of the respective first BLUP per

case has no relation to the respective year of HSR implementation, suggesting an individual treatment of given potentials. Yet, considering an average elaboration phase of 3.4 years until the BLUP in this sample become legally binding, there are some hints of anticipating the potentials of HSR. Thus, within the ISA, the BLUP related to HSR are even more numerous than those without reference. However, there are several BLUP unrelated to HSR – although primarily located in the WSA. This fact presumes that HSR implementation often coincides with an already prosperous phase indicating strong general planning impetus (Ribalaygua et al., 2020).

Despite context sensitivity, the sample expresses similarities concerning overall spatial impacts in descending order. The character of newly built HSR stations in Vaihingen(Enz) (73.3ha) and Montabaur (43.2ha) is shown by the two largest total area sizes. Erfurt (41.2ha) and C-Messe/Deutz (37.8ha) are behind with large land potentials, often on abandoned sites. These are followed by the stations of Siegburg (29.0ha) and Fulda (20.0ha), also centrally located but in much smaller cities. In these established station areas, notable spatial impacts of HSR are evident, but types (a) and (b) are roughly balanced with type (c). Although Bamberg (14.1ha) and Ingolstadt (0.3ha) are also located in existing inner-city structures, the spatial impacts of HSR have been minor so far.

Finally, projects currently not yet realised but planned remain of great interest. Only a few are mentioned here. Developments of higher-value services (2.5ha) remain to be realised directly at Siegburg's station's rear side. In addition, the preparatory land-use plan of Vaihingen(Enz) contains stipulations for further commercial and higher-value services (23ha) and residential areas (19ha). Moreover, 19 of the 65 BLUP were in preparation at data gathering, especially in the recently equipped station areas (Erfurt and Bamberg). Furthermore, more sites of industrial or railway-related use near the stations (Fulda, Ingolstadt, Bamberg and Erfurt) might be potential land, but whose development horizon is unclear.

All in all, the spatial impacts of HSR on station areas are manifold, but highly case-dependent. They appear with temporal variations and rapidly decline spatially outwards. Furthermore, certain patterns of use can be identified across the cases, but high individuality remains regarding the type of land-use transformation.

Municipal planning governance and other inherent preconditions (Q2)

The case studies reveal distinct, albeit different, municipal governance to address HSR through significant planning impetus and strategic alignment. A homogenous planning strategy cannot be identified; rather, case-specific handling based on individual locational factors and preconditions prevails. The planning governance for the two station areas within core cities (C-Messe/Deutz and Erfurt) equips them more with typical core-city functions. In contrast, for cities located outside the urban regions or in the vicinity of a core city, reachable

direct connected metropolitan areas within a certain travel time via HSR seem to be more considerable as, in addition to geographical proximity, network externalities become conceivable owing to relational proximity (Bentlage et al., 2013). Additionally, most cases got a strong upgraded connection to major airports (Frankfurt am Main, Cologne/Bonn and Düsseldorf) via HSR, improving international accessibility and possible benefits, especially for the knowledge economy (Grove, 2019). Consequently, these HSR stations reveal certain metropolisation impulses (Garmendia et al., 2008; Mohíno et al., 2014) driven by spill-over effects of HSR represented in the planning purposes of the BLUP.

These observations ally with the intention of establishing knowledge-intensive activities in the station areas. Montabaur, C-Messe/Deutz and Erfurt clearly demonstrate these tendencies by locating many workplaces in higher-value service sectors. Additionally, Siegburg and Vaihingen(Enz) also intend this direction with built-up use yet to be realised. Not only the establishment of office buildings but also of meeting facilities like hotels and congress venues (Fulda, Siegburg, C-Messe/Deutz and Erfurt), enabling temporary spatial proximity and interaction (Grove, 2019), can be deemed part of this observed development path. The new establishment of (public) R&D institutions as a further component of knowledge-intensive activities could not be observed within the given station areas and analysis period. However, we should bear in mind that the institutions already established profit from the increased accessibility.

However, the expressions differ according to local and territorial characteristics. Thus, strengthening of station profiles can be recognised. New mixed-use or commercial districts appear to be the predominant pursuit of planning. Nevertheless, mono-functional residential districts more often tend to be placed outside. The central location of some stations leads to high integration into the urban fabric but to a limited supply of potential sites and vice versa. The widespread project-based character and some outstanding projects complement more ordinary urban development processes.

Besides anticipating municipal planning, there are pronounced inherent preconditions influencing urban development. The combination of and interplay between the supply of land, local constraints and characteristics and construction work at the stations constitute the main influencing factors. Regardless of the type of land-use transformation, the supply of land is the biggest lever causing the spatial impacts of HSR. This required absorptive capacity is expressed in various manifestations of land management by the municipal planning through BLUP. Besides (a), the development of hitherto open spaces, or (c), the retention of existing use, (b), the conversion of existing structures, is regularly subject to greater efforts and requires higher governance. The high degree of imperviousness in established HSR station areas hampers new developments. In contrast to other countries, the German HSR network only possesses very few newly built HSR stations, which means completely different initial conditions. Therefore, landowner involvement or municipal ownership are important

preconditions (*operational connectivity*, Loukaitou-Sideris and Peters (2020)). Under certain conditions, the municipalities can exercise formal instruments to buy sites from private actors or *Deutsche Bahn* (often the owner of former railway sites) steering desired urban development. The Urban Rehabilitation Measures and Urban Development Measures are powerful instruments facilitating municipalities to implement their urban planning designs more coherently and efficiently (Pahl-Weber & Henckel, 2008). Local constraints and characteristics are further factors, but they remain highly context-sensitive, ranging from hard (built environment) to softer factors (planning restrictions).

Following the Node-Place Model (Bertolini, 1999), the node function is visible from two perspectives. First, we see the pursuit of good embeddedness of HSR into PT, e.g. shown by the better integration of central bus stations nearby (*intermodal connectivity*, Loukaitou-Sideris and Peters (2020)). In this context, the limited competence of municipalities must be considered, since higher-level transportation authorities are responsible for services like regional rail and exclusively the local PT (tram-/subway, buses) resides with the municipalities or districts. Second, the corroboration of PT in newly erected districts is crucial for developments in the TOD sense. This is visible, since there are references to PT integration in the explanation memoranda. Aspirations to enhance the place function, e.g. enhancing public spaces and connection axes (*spatial connectivity*, Loukaitou-Sideris and Peters (2020)), substantially occur, as municipalities have the competence of fostering urban qualities.

Finally, a critical consideration is required for impacts to be induced exclusively by HSR. The criticisms regarding HSR of being more of a reinforcer of ongoing urban developments (Ribalaygua et al., 2020) or the concern of merely 'transit adjacent' rather than 'transit oriented' developments (Peters & Novy, 2012) can be partially alleviated. The most investigated urban developments are initiated and shaped by HSR, e.g. large-scale office buildings (C-Messe/Deutz, Montabaur, Erfurt and Ingolstadt), residential areas (Vaihingen(Enz) and Fulda) or hotels and congress venues (Fulda and Siegburg). Framing or marketing titles are distinctive indices for this deduction. Additionally, every case provides at least a few urban developments – no matter whether realised or not – related to HSR. In the same way, enhancements concerning the node-place functions of stations are in line with this.

Nevertheless, for a few projects, especially those without a BLUP, this cannot be clarified based on the available documents and we must consider other possible factors for urban development. Therefore, how the station areas would appear in the absence of HSR is interesting but remains unanswered. Again, the differing pressure on local development expresses the context sensitivity and some developments would surely have been initiated without HSR. In other cases, HSR could take the role of urban development's final driver.

In most cases, municipal planning governance copes with the HSR potentials in a distinctive but often individual manner with strategic alignment. The decisive requirement that municipal planning consciously steers and negotiates the inherent preconditions and

influencing factors, such as supply of land or local constraints and characteristics for successful urban development in HSR station areas, is recognisable.

Conclusions

This article examines the spatial impacts on urban development in station areas driven by the potentials of HSR and their addressing of municipal planning governance to unleash urban development. The analyses of binding land-use plans (BLUP) as the embodiment of municipal planning and underlying strategies provide insights for HSR in Germany on a narrowly defined spatial scale for the first time.

Referring to HSR illustrates the intention to translate gains in accessibility and increased attractiveness into urban development impulses. Our study reveals comprehensive and varied urban developments with the greatest extent in the immediate station areas (ISA). The formation of agglomeration effects and new centralities with significantly higher densities, and mixed and commercial use are underlined. Conversely, residential use tends to be placed outside. Certain time lags and case-specific paths must be considered, as we recognise both initial and long-lasting planning impetus, with many BLUP becoming legally binding around HSR implementation and the following 15 years, but 30% of the BLUP are currently in preparation. In particular, the conversion of previously used land to new uses is time-consuming.

Simultaneously, these observed spatial impacts uncover certain challenges and inherent preconditions. Therefore, we demonstrated that accompanying municipal planning governance is considered promising to cope with these interdependencies. This especially includes the utilisation of land, use of (in)formal instruments and concepts, generating urban qualities, mitigation of potential drawbacks and stakeholder integration.

Unlike previous studies, the analyses presented underpin specific findings for HSR research based on the situation in Germany: The spatial impacts occur on a rather small scale due to the existing structures and smaller plots of land. Additionally, the impacts are, in a sense, lower, as the existing stations often had good accessibility beforehand. The cases of Erfurt and Montabaur appear as counter-examples, with available space combined with stringent municipal planning governance. Approvingly, a larger initial investment or high-quality anchor utilisation also emerges as an immensely beneficial driver for further developments. But, in summary, planning for station areas is not well integrated in Germany, as the responsibilities are separated between *Deutsche Bahn* and the municipalities, which can only react to operational schedules.

Several limitations of the study can pave the way for future research. Some (smaller) urban developments remain elusive due to the present study design if they are fulfilled without a BLUP. Further investigations, with e.g. remote sensing data, may observe these spatial impacts. Also, it became clear that a spatially narrowly defined station area is sufficient to

observe the main urban development impulses emanating from HSR, at least for the situation in Germany. Furthermore, possible deeper underlying processes or the difficulties of municipal governance cannot be extracted in detail from the present documents. Further qualitative approaches (e.g. expert interviews) may shed more light on such issues.

Nonetheless, this article contributes to the small-scale assessment of urban developments by HSR by showing a method for empirical observation below the level of aggregated statistical data using the example of spatially referenced BLUP in Germany. Likewise, the methodological distinction between realised developments and those not yet realised is expedient for further studies, as this approach reveals the gap between municipal planning intentions and the actual manifestations of station areas. Thus, from the perspective of municipal governance, the empirical findings suggest the benefits of anticipating the advent of HSR and the rewarding application of planning instruments to transform the node character of HSR stations into place building and further gains for municipalities.

Against the backdrop of further HSR expansion in Germany, our analyses indicate that the potential arising from the massive investments in rail infrastructure for urban development in the station areas should be exploited more strategically and better coordinated than before. For this purpose, it is necessary to bring key actors – particularly the municipality, *Deutsche Bahn* and other central landowners in the ISA – together at an early stage prior to opening or upgrading the HSR station to explore development intentions and work towards consensual project development. For the municipalities, urban development in the station area should then be consciously embedded in strategic concepts and implementation should be closely flanked by formal planning and urban development legal instruments. However, as successful urban development in the HSR station areas shows (e.g. in Montabaur and currently in Erfurt), this can be an appropriate way to use the accessibility improvements as a catalyst for urban development.

Acknowledgements

This paper is part of the research project "Brain Train? High-speed rail stations as focal points of the knowledge economy" funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) – project no. 437850433.

The authors are grateful to the project partners Johannes Moser, Alain Thierstein, and Fabian Wenner (Chair of Urban Development, Technical University of Munich) for the discussions and acknowledge the research assistance provided by Moritz Twente.

The authors would like to thank the organisers and participants of the ARL:Univie International Summer School "Urban and Regional Infrastructures" held in Vienna in September 2021 for their valuable comments. Furthermore, we also thank the employees of the planning departments in Fulda, Ingolstadt, and Montabaur for their support and two

anonymous reviewers for their very helpful comments, which helped us improve the paper's quality.

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Appendix

maintaining/advancing inner-city functions

quarter development (mixed-use, planned)
conversion of allotment area

Perfekter Standort (Perfect Location), commercial area

preparatory land-use plan: commercial area

preparatory land-use plan: higher-value services

preparatory land-use plan: residential area

former railway station

Type of land-use transformation

- Development of hitherto open spaces
- Conversion of existing structures
- Retention of existing uses
- +1 Δt year of opening

Type of land use

- Commercial (existing)
- Commercial (not yet realised)
- Residential (existing)
- Residential (not yet realised)
- Mixed areas (existing)

- Mixed areas (not yet realised)
- Special areas (existing)
- Special areas (not yet realised)
- Other (existing)
- Other (not yet realised)

Station Areas

- Entrances
- Isochrone 800m
- Isochrone 300m
- Grid 3x3km
- Tracks

i.p. = in preparation

Other = public facilities + traffic areas + green spaces

Type of land-use transformation	Type of land use	Station Areas	
● Development of hitherto open spaces	■ Commercial (existing)	● Entrances	i.p. = in preparation
●● Conversion of existing structures	■ Commercial (not yet realised)	■ Isochrone 800m	
●● Retention of existing uses	■ Residential (existing)	■ Isochrone 300m	Other = public facilities + traffic areas + green spaces
+1 Δt year of opening	■ Residential (not yet realised)	■ Grid 3x3km	
	■ Mixed areas (existing)	— Tracks	
	■ Mixed areas (not yet realised)		
	■ Special areas (existing)		
	■ Special areas (not yet realised)		
	■ Other (existing)		
	■ Other (not yet realised)		

